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Two unpublished documents – the reports of the Société Royale of medicine and the Académie Royale des Sciences on *Entomologia Parisiensis* and their implications for zoological nomenclature

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15004141>

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Abstract: Published in 1762 by E.-L. Geoffroy *Histoire abregée des insectes...* is one of the most important works of eighteenth-century zoology, both because of the number of species described and the use of the Linnean system. However, the descriptions were published in French and the work itself had a format that was impractical for field research. In 1785 A.-F. Fourcroy published *Entomologia Parisiensis* based on it, adding not only Latin descriptions but several hundred new species. Since then, there has been a dispute whether *Entomologia Parisiensis* is an original work or merely an adaptation of *Histoire abregée des insectes*. The article analyzes the reports of the Académie Royale des Sciences and Académie royale de Médecine preceding the publication of this work. The originality of *Entomologia Parisiensis* was clearly demonstrated, and it was established which species should be considered as described by Fourcroy and which were originally described by Geoffroy.

Key words: History of entomology, *Entomologia parisiensis*, Geoffroy, Fourcroy, Linnean nomenclature, archives’ research.

The work of Étienne-Louis Geoffroy (1727-1810) *Histoire abregée des insectes: qui se trouvent aux environs de Paris: dans laquelle ces animaux sont rangés suivant un ordre méthodique* quickly became a reference for entomology as much for the reason for the number of species described but also by its method and the use of the Linnaean system. Note that the word “entomology” and “insects” are used in the very Aristotelian sense of the eighteenth century which still also includes other taxonomic groups, e.g., arachnids or myriapods (DROUIN 2014). Naturalists of the time recognized that E.-L. Geoffroy was at the origin of a new method of classification. An anonymous note conserved in Geoffroy’s biographical file at l’Académie de Médecine in Paris, informs that:

...entomology and conchology owe him work that place him at the forefront. E.L. Geoffroy had in fact, with regard to articulated animals, a flash of genius which made him discover a most remarkable classification: I am going to talk about his division of beetles into four groups established on the number of articles which make up the tarsus of these little beings; pentamers, tetramers, triomers, heteromers. Linnaeus did not do better, as for plants, in his sexual classification.

The Central Library of Muséum national d'Histoire naturelle in Paris preserves a eulogy of this scholar, this eight-page offprint bears the exlibris of Georges Cuvier and a handwritten inscription informing that the note was published in 1810 in the Bibliothèque médicale. We can read there:

comparative anatomy and the study of natural history were Mr. Geoffroy's leisure activities; it was in his early years that he gathered a number of observations on the characters and maneuvers of insects, observations which served him well to establish a new method of entomological classification based on that of Linnaeus, but which was only published a long time later, in 1762, in two volumes, in-4, at the request of the author famous Bernard de Jussieu. Linnaeus recommended reading this work to his students; the public followed his advice (ANONYMOUS 1810).

The *Histoire abrégée des insectes* had several editions with slightly different titles

Histoire abrégée des insectes: qui se trouvent aux environs de Paris: dans laquelle ces animaux sont rangés suivant un ordre méthodique, published in 1762 by "Durand, rue de Foin, la première porte cochère en entrant par la rue S. Jacques, au Griffon" and *Histoire abrégée des insectes dans laquelle ces animaux sont rangés suivant un ordre méthodique*, published by "Durand, neveu, rue S. Jaques, à la Sagesse". A second edition was prepared by Geoffroy: *Histoire abrégée des insectes Paris: dans laquelle ces Animaux sont rangés suivant un ordre méthodique. Nouvelle Édition, revue, corrigée et augmentée d'un supplément considérable*, published in, en An VII (1798/1799), by "Callixte- Volland, Libraire, Quai des Augustin, N°. 24" and "Rémont, Libraire, Quai des Augustin, N°. 41", the next edition, *Histoire abrégée des insectes Paris: dans laquelle ces Animaux sont rangés suivant un ordre méthodique. Nouvelle Édition, revue, corrigée et augmentée d'un supplément considérable*, published in 1800 (An 9) by "Delalain, Fils, Libraire, quai des Augustin, N°. 29."

AGUILAR and RAIMBAULT (1990) analyzed these various editions, concluding that the 1764 edition is simply a reprint of the 1762 edition and that the 1798/1799 and 1800 editions are identical, as well as:

This second edition is a simple reprint of the first edition (to the point that the final page of the previous edition bears the same signature which, as a result, is of no use) to which has been added, in each volume, a supplement and a list of errata: T. I., pp. 514-545 (i.e. 104 species, T. II, pp. 681-734 (i.e. 152 species). The binomial nomenclature of Fourcroy (1785) is included in these supplements. There is also a quarto print, in four volumes, with wide margins on watermarked paper "papier du Marais De Lagarde Lainé et Compagnie". Only the title pages are recomposed (AGUILAR & RAIMBAULT 1990).

The work of É.-L. Geoffroy was a very important contribution to the introduction of Linnaean systematics, however it does not use binomial nomenclature. The name of the genera is followed by several Latin adjectives intended to characterize the species. The descriptions were written in French. The editions of the *Histoire abrégée des Insectes* had the in quarto format, which was impractical for taking the book into the field. In 1785, Antoine-Francois Fourcroy (1755-1789) published, based on the work of É.-L. Geoffroy,

Entomologia Parisiensis; sive catalogus insectorum quae in agro Parisiensi reperiuntur; secundum methodum Geoffraeanam in sectiones, genera & species distributus; cui addita sunt nomina trivalia & fere trecentae novae species. Edente A. F. de Fourcroy. Note that the work does not provide any information on the publisher or printer. As the title indicates, A.-F. Fourcroy classified insects in his book “according to Geoffroy’s method”.

The natural sciences of the eighteenth century were strongly marked by the search for “methods” and “systems” of classification. The system proposed by É.-L. Geoffroy was one of the best known and most used. A.-F. Fourcroy returned to this system and its description in the fifth volume of *Éléments d’Histoire Naturelle et de Chimie*. He even presented a synthetic table of this method (FOURCROY 1789).

Since then, a question has arisen: who is really the author of the *Entomologia Parisiensis*? What is the part of A.-F. Fourcroy’s work? Is it only a question of formatting and a version adapted to the work of a naturalist in the field with the application of the Linnaean binominal nomenclature of the *Histoire abrégée des insectes* or is the contribution of A.F. F Fourcroy sufficiently great to talk about an original work?

These questions are all the more important as the answers have a direct implication on the nomenclature of several hundred species because the *Histoire abrégée des insectes* should be considered for the names of species (but not for the names of the genera) as a publication “not available” according to the criteria of the International Code of Zoological Nomenclature and it is the *Entomologia Parisiensis* which thus became the first original publication for these taxa. Let us also remember that in the eighteenth century the rules of reproduction, the use of works or quotations were far from our standards today and such a resumption of a work by another author was a common practice and not was not shocking or perceived as unethical (DASZKIEWICZ 2015).

Some of the authors treat Fourcroy’s book only as a simple abridgement of É.-L. Geoffroy’s work: *not to mention Fourcroy’s Entomologia parisiensis* (1785), *an abridged translation of Geoffroy’s work* (MULSANT & REY 1864) or *even His Entomologia parisiensis is only a Latin index of Histoire abrégée of Geoffroy, whose French names received the Linnaean form* (FAUVEL, BOURGEOIS & BUYSSON 1868).

Confusion also exists in library catalogs, considered as references. The catalog of the Bibliothèque Nationale de France BNF cites A.F. Fourcroy as the sole author of the work. On the other hand, the Muscat catalog of the Muséum national d’Histoire naturelle libraries, without however giving any information on this choice, cites É.-L. Geoffroy as the author of *Entomologia Parisiensis* and treats A.F. Fourcroy as “contributor” and “scientific editor” and gives *Histoire abrégée des insectes* as an “other title” of this work.

SMEATON (1962), biographer of A.-F. Fourcroy, sees this story from another angle. He states that although chemistry was the main subject of his research, A.-F. Fourcroy was also interested in natural history and frequently went on field trips around Paris, often accompanied by his friend, botanist, entomologist and politician, Ambroise Marie Francois Joseph Palisot de Beauvois (1752-1820):

Fourcroy noticed that Geoffroy’s account of the insects of the Paris region was incomplete and he intended to publish a supplement, but he gathered so much new information that in 1785 he published the completely revised Entomologia Parisiensis, which included 300 additional species. He retained Geoffroy’s classification and gave a brief description of the insects in Latin, but by omitting Geoffroy’s lengthy comments he was able to reduce the work to two small volumes which could be carried in one’s pocket (SMEATON 1962).

One of the most important aspects of the scientific revolution in the eighteenth century was field work. Naturalists increasingly abandoned the study of the “curiosities” of cabinets and did not treat the works of Aristotle and the scholars of the Renaissance as the only source of the description of the living world but more and more often went to them -themselves in the field. This change required new tools including portable books. Fourcroy’s approach is part of this logic of natural history of the time. Furthermore, we can note that it was a successful bet because Fourcroy not only published a book that was easy to carry in the field but also inexpensive because it sold for five livres tournois (see *Gazette de France* of August 12, 1785 p. 274).

A.M.F.J. Palisot de Beauvois thus remembered the origin of *Entomologia Parisiensis*. Let us note in his sentences another motivation for preparing this book, a desire to complete É.-L. Geoffroy’s work adding the missing species:

After leaving college our bond strengthened all the more as we had the same love for the study of natural history. Mr. Fourcroy, who eagerly grasped everything he undertook and who burned with the desire to try his strength, saw with a sort of regret that Mr. Geoffroy’s immortal work on insects was found to be incomplete and that he missing a large number of species found around Paris. He conceived the project of adding a supplement to it. He told me about it. We stopped making at least three excursions a week together around Paris. This is how one of the first works that Mr. Fourcroy published shortly after was undertaken. He had the greatest veneration for Mr. Geoffroy, whom he called his master. A few months before his death, while chatting with him about the new entomological systems, he said to me “no matter what we do, we will always have to return, at least for the major divisions, to the method of Geoffroy, this author seems to me, for centuries, what Tournefort is for plants. (PALISOT de BEAUVOIS 1810).

It is justified to ask the question why É.-L. Geoffroy himself did not prepare such a work despite having this project. He was at the time in Paris one of the most sought-after medical practitioners, a very active member of the Société Royale de la Médecine, he published poems in Latin (GEOFFROY 1771) and he carried out various research on plants and materia medica. According to A.-F. FOURCROY (1785), É.-L. Geoffroy “Diverted by his medical activities, so beneficial for his fellow citizens, he was unable to complete the work he had undertaken” (French translation AGUILAR & RAIMBAULT 1990). However, he also continued his zoological research and explained that:

After having published the Histoire abrégée des insectes : qui se trouvent aux environs de Paris a few years ago, my project was to continue the same work on Worms, & to give the Public the History of these Animals. The class of Worms is similar to that of Insects, and becomes all the more interesting as it is perhaps the least known until now (GEOFFROY 1767).

We can therefore think that it was simply a lack of time that did not allow É.-L. Geoffroy to prepare a suitable version to take to the field. The idea of such “portable entomology” was based on certain botanical books and then particularly on the *Botanicon Parisense*, the posthumous work of Sebastien Vaillant (1669-1722), a reference, cited as a model by A.-F. Fourcroy.

The *Entomologia Parisiensis* contains at the beginning, what was the custom of the time, the extract from the registers of the Société Royale de Médecine:

The Société Royale de Médecine having heard the session held at the Louvre on June 23 this month, reading a very advantageous report made by MM. Geoffroy & Maudyt, on a work by M. De Fourcroy, entitled: Entomologia Parisiensis, sive Catalogus insectorum

quae circa Lutetiam reperiuntur; Etc. thought that this Work was very worthy of his approval. In witness whereof I have signed this present. In Paris, this June 28, 1785. Signed, Vicq d'Azir; Perpetual Secretary, as well as the register of the Academy of Sciences:

The Commissioners appointed by the Academy, having reported to it on a work by M. de Fourcroy, entitled: Entomologia Parisiensis, it judged this work worthy of its approval, and to appear under its Privilege. I certify this extract as conforming to the original and the records of the Academy. July 13, 1785. Signed, the Marquis de Condorcet.

We thought that finding the originals of these reports could help elucidate the problem of the authorship of the description of the species in the *Entomologia Parisiensis*, especially since É.-L. Geoffroy was one of the co-authors, with Pierre Jacques Claude Mauduyt de la Varenne (1732-1792), doctor, pioneer of the use of electricity in medicine and naturalist, of the report for the Société Royale de Médecine:

The Society having commissioned Mr. Geoffroy and me to examine a work entitled Entomologia Parisiensis sive Catalogus insectorum quae circa Lutetiam parisiensis [probably a mistake because it had to be “reperiuntur” as in the printed original], which was presented to it by Mr. de Fourcroy, we have become aware of such a work.

Mr. de Fourcroy executed the plan that Geoffroy had planned for a long time, to present in a single volume to be taken to the countryside, the abbreviated description, catalog method, of the insects found around Paris, or the extract from his great work in 4th grade, on this class of animals. He added the method proper to recognize insects, and it will be distributed in 6 sections like Mr. Geoffroy. The order of the genera, their characters are also absolutely the same. We add to this edition particular names or species of epithets that are like calling trivial according to Linnaeus. This work written in Latin, like most of those of the same genre, contains more than two hundred and fifty new species; these have been distinguished by an asterisk. Mr. de Fourcroy took care to add to the Latin generic and trivial names which determine each species, the Latin indication or of the plant that the plant each of them inhabits + in order to facilitate the gentle study of this part of natural history. This work, comparable to the Parisian Botanicon and which was lacking in France, seems to us to be more useful than the latter in relation to the part it deals with, because the Botanicon presents the plants only in alphabetical order and without any methodical description, while the entomology which concerns us teaches us to distinguish from six sections and gives the method appropriate to fulfill this object. We therefore believe that it could be pleasant to lovers of Natural History and that it deserves to be printed with the approval and under the privilege of the Society. Deliberated at the Louvre on June 23, 1785. Geoffroy Mauduyt.

The second report is transcribed in extenso in the session records (August 13, 1785) and its handwritten original is kept in the pocket as is customary at the Academy of Sciences. It was prepared by Louis Jean-Marie Daubenton (1716-1799) and Pierre Marie Auguste Broussonet (1761-1807):

We have examined, by order of the Academy, a work by Mr. Fourcroy on the insects of the environs of Paris, entitled Entomologia Parisiensis... Mr. Geoffroy is the first in France to have arranged the greatest number of insects in a methodical order: he published the history of those found in the environs of Paris, he established genera and species by short and characteristic sentences. Mr. Defourcroy kept the same sentences in his Entomologia Parisiensis, he reported to each insect the indication of the place and most often of the plant where it can be found, and he added the dimensions of their body according to the work of Mr. Geoffroy. Mr. Defourcroy had said in his preface that Mr. Geoffroy himself worked on the

Entomologia, that he added to the description of each species of insect, the name which suits it and that he had denied in his history of insects where each species is distinguished only by a specific phrase.

Mr. Defourcroy is not only the Editor of this work, but he has also added more than 300 species of insects which are not described in Mr. Geoffroy's history and which he makes known following the method of this author.

Although several works on the same subject have appeared since the history of Mr. Geoffroy, in which one sometimes finds even more detailed descriptions of the same insects, we believe, however, that the *Entomologia* of Mr. Defourcroy, which is given to the public, even considered as an abridgement of the history of Mr. Geoffroy, can only be very useful to naturalists who devote themselves to the study of insects from the surroundings of Paris, that it will serve to spread the taste for this beautiful part of natural history and that it could be considered in Entomology as the *Botanicon parisiensis* of Vaillant in Botany; we therefore think that the *Entomologia parisiensis* of Mr. Fourcroy deserves the approval of the Academy and to be printed under its privilege.

It took only 17 days from the permission of the Academy (July 13) until the presentation of *Entomologia Parisiensis* in print because the records inform us that on Saturday, July 30, 1785 "M. Defurcroy presented the catalog of insects from the surroundings of Paris in 2 volumes, in 12".

These reports allow us to establish unequivocally that:

1. A.-F. Fourcroy is the sole author of the *Entomologia Parisiensis*.

2. The role of É.-L. Geoffroy and his *Histoire abrégée des insectes* are well recognized because, just as in the introduction to the *Entomologia Parisiensis*, it is clearly stated that A.-F. Fourcroy wanted to adapt É.-L. Geoffroy's work to the needs of field work and that it was É.-L. Geoffroy who added the binomial names to the species described in the *Histoire abrégée des insectes*.

3. Nowhere is it stated that É.-L. Geoffroy contributed to the addition of the new species or to their description.

Who is the author of the taxa described in the *Entomologia Parisiensis*? In the literature we find several interpretations: "Fourcroy, 1785", "Geoffroy, 1785", "Geoffroy in Fourcroy 1785", "Geoffroy & Fourcroy, 1785". The discussion of this problem is very old and it even goes back to the period before the very first International Congress of Zoology (in Paris in 1899) and the creation of the International Commission on Zoological Nomenclature in 1895 during the third congress in Leiden:

*A word more on the vicious names that Mr. de Kiesenwetter points out. Ecailleux violet of Geoffroy! and doubtless all the name of this author such as the Livrée d'Ancre, the Arlequin velu, the Drap mortuaire, etc. German entomologists do not seem to know at all or know very little of the work of the father of French entomology, the contemporary of Linnaeus, the inventor of the tarsal system adopted by all the entomologists who followed him and which alone would suffice for his glory. This work, the most important that France had until Latreille, can still be consulted with profit by entomologists, and beginners will draw from it valuable notions on all branches of entomology. By attacking the vernacular names of Geoffroy that he would like to ridicule, the author of the Dresden code forgets or ignores that these names were Latinized by Fourcroy, helped by Geoffroy himself, in his *Entomologia Parisiensis*. The illustrious author of the *Système des connaissances chimiques*,*

a very distinguished naturalist himself, did not believe he was deviating by publishing his *Catalogue des insectes des environs de Paris*, which is in some way only an abridgement of Geoffroy's work with its Latinized names. The nomenclature still awaits the reestablishment of the names of which Geoffroy has priority. If the authors do not want to go back to the vernacular names of 1762, one cannot have any objections for the same names Latinized in 1785 by Fourcroy. I therefore implore the authors to render Geoffroy the justice that is due to him by restoring his names to the nomenclature; for my part I will not fail to do so. (REICHE 1859).

AGUILAR & RAIMBAULT (1990) advocate the use of "Geoffroy in Fourcroy, 1785" by referring to article 51 of the Code of Nomenclature and relying on the sentences from the introduction to the *Entomologia Parisiensis*:

The author himself added the common names, often Linnaean, that he had neglected in his great work" and "In addition, over the past 20 years many new species have been discovered in the Parisian countryside, which exceed those described in the Histoire des insectes in-4°, I have taken care to mark them with an asterisk. I have added the dimensions of the species and their habitat; thus, this Catalogue presents a greater number of species and a revised nomenclature relative to the great in-4° work and I recognize that this improvement is essentially the work of the famous Geoffroy. Let us note once again that nowhere is it said that É.-L. Geoffroy is the author of the description of the new species in the *Entomologia Parisiensis* and this is a condition defined by the Code in order to establish the paternity of the description. Furthermore, we can note that the same author spoke less categorically in other publications:

In reality, Fourcroy took up Geoffroy's vernacular names by adding a Linnaean binomial while retaining the Latin diagnoses. In addition, in agreement with Geoffroy, he added 256 new species. The additions will also be taken up as a supplement by Geoffroy in the second edition (1799 and 1800) of his "Histoire abrégée des insectes" (AGUILAR 1999).

Closely related to this work, we must mention Antoine François de Fourcroy (1755-1809) who published in 1785 two small books Entomologia Parisiensis; sive catalogus insectorum quae in agro Parisiensi reperiuntur; secundum methodum Geoffraeanam... This set actually represents a fauna from the surroundings of Paris where, in the first edition, there are 118 genera and 1325 species to which 250 new species will be added. The major divisions are borrowed from Linnaeus's drafts. Geoffroy, one of the first naturalists to accept the Linnaean system, initiated the consideration of the number of tarsi and introduced the use of the mention of size which, without being a precise characteristic, nevertheless helps with recognition. Fourcroy, in his abridgement (1785), took up the vernacular names of his model by Latinizing the binomial; These additions were made with Geoffroy's agreement (AGUILAR 2006).

In these quotes A.-F. Fourcroy is recognized as the author of the additions, the author who worked "in agreement with Geoffroy" or "with Geoffroy's agreement."

Some of the generic names of beetles and crustaceans described in the *Histoire abrégée des insectes: qui se trouve aux environs de Paris* have been the subject of comments published in the Bulletin of zoological nomenclature (BROOKS 1992, HOLTHUIS 1992, KRELL 1992, LASALLE 1992, POPE 1992, RAGGE 1992, SILFVERBERG 1992, TUBBS 1992, KERZHNER 1993) in favor of their conservation. However, it should not be forgotten that the situation of published specific names is different because according to the rules of the Code, they

do not meet the necessary criteria to be retained. Who is the author of the descriptions of these species? It should be noted that this problem is not limited to the species described in the *Histoire abrégé des insectes*: which are found in the vicinity of Paris, but also concerns a certain number of molluscs described in the *Traité sommaire des coquilles: tant fluviatiles que terrestre, qui se trouve aux environs de Paris*.

The reports of the Société Royale de Médecine and the Académie Royale des Sciences on the *Entomologia Parisiensis*, found in the archives of the Académie de Médecine and the Académie des Sciences, provide direct proof that for the new species added in this work, we cannot consider É.-L. Geoffroy as the author of their descriptions. We must therefore consider them in two separate groups.

The species described in the *Histoire abrégée des insectes* and taken up by A.-F. Fourcroy and the species described for the first time (see table) in the *Entomologia Parisiensis*. For the first group we can follow the recommendations of AGUILAR & RAIMBAULT (1990) and apply article 51 of the Code and consider as the author “Geoffroy in Fourcroy, 1785” but for the second group the author’s name must be “Fourcroy, 1785”.

To designate the species that are “new” in the *Entomologia Parisiensis* we made a comparison between this work and the supplement of the second edition of the *Histoire abrégée des insectes*. This seemed all the more important to us since É.-L. Geoffroy marked the new species with an asterisk and yet several species not marked with an asterisk were taken up by É.-L. Geoffroy as new and they must also be considered as described by Fourcroy in 1785.

First of all, we must recall the information we have on this second edition. In reality, the text is a simple reprint of the 1762 version. So, it is only the supplement that changes. The changes are not reported in the text itself, so neither *Entomologia Parisiensis* nor the other works cited in the text are present in the sources cited at the beginning of the text. The supplement is mostly just a resumption of the additions of A.-F. Fourcroy. É.-L. Geoffroy, apart from adding the descriptions in French, completing the bibliography and sometimes changing the location of the species or the recognition of synonymy, has added to the literature only two species (*Melolontha variabilis*, *Phalaena camilla*) and two new species (*Tinea hesperidum* and *Tipula marmorata*).

We know very little about the origin of this second edition of the *Histoire abrégée des insectes*. É.-L. Geoffroy, arrested during the Revolution and then placed under surveillance, took refuge “near Soissons” in Chéry Chartheuse (Aisne) where he continued to work on writings on diseases and devoted himself to caring for the needy.

Once the terror was over, he became (on April 24, 1798) “associate of the section of anatomy and zoology” of the Institut National. He became a doctor helping all the poor and sick in the surrounding area.

His correspondence, preserved at the Académie des Sciences, with Antoine- Laurent Jussieu (1748-1836) proves that he took care of botanizing and prepared an important herbarium. He even became the mayor of his commune. We have no information to know his involvement in the second edition. The attached table summarizes the relationships between the species described by A.F. Fourcroy and those of É.-L. Geoffroy. In bold we marked orthographic differences between the names in two works.

FOURCROY - species signaled as new by «*» FOURCROY - gatunek oznaczony jako nowy przez «*»	Page Strona	GEOFFROY 1799 and 1800 GEOFFROY 1799 i 1800	Page Strona
Platycerus pygmaeus	3	Platycerus pygmaeus	514
Scarabaeus sulcatus	13	Scarabaeus sulcatus	515
Dermestes suturatus	23	Dermestes suturatus	515
Dermestes trisulcus	23	Dermestes trisulcus	515
Dermestes fasciatus	23	Dermestes fasciatus	515
Dermestes scapularis	23	Dermestes scapularis	516
Dermestes pygmaeus	24	Dermestes pygmaeus	516
Dermestes thoracicus	24	Dermestes thoracicus	516
Dermestes testudinarius	24	Dermestes testudinarius	517
Dermestes tricolor	24	Dermestes tricolor	517
Dermestes tessellatus signaled without «*»	25	Dermestes tessellatus	517
Dermestes semicoleopterus signaled without «*»	25	Dermestes semicoleopterus	517
Dermestes dimidiatus (s.a.)	25	Dermestes dimidiatus	518
Cucujus ater	34	Cucujus ater	518
Cucujus dentatus	34	Cucujus dentatus	518
Elater rachifer	39	Elater rachifer	519
Elater melanophtalmos	39	Elater melanophtalmos	519
Elater fuscus	39	Elater fuscus	520
Elater villosus signaled without «*»	40	Elater villosus	520
Buprestis longicornis	42	Buprestis longicornis	520
Buprestis episcopalis	48	Buprestis episcopalis	520
Buprestis suturatus	49	Buprestis suturatus	521
Buprestis marginatus	49	Buprestis marginatus	521
Buprestis scapularis	50	Buprestis scapularis	521
Buprestis contractus signaled without «*»	50	Buprestis contractus	521
Buprestis lunulatus	51	Buprestis lunulatus	522
Buprestis foveatus	52	Buprestis foveatus	522
Buprestis capitatus	52	Buprestis capitatus	522
Buprestis maxillosus	53	Buprestis maxillosus	522
Buprestis plateosus	53	Buprestis plateosus	523
Buprestis fumosus	54	Buprestis fumosus	523
Buprestis aeruginosus signaled without «*»	54	Buprestis aeruginosus	523
Buprestis leporinus	55		
Buprestis conexus	55	Buprestis conexus	523
Buprestis rubescens	56		
Buprestis rosaceus	56	Buprestis rosaceus	524
Buprestis rusticus	56	Buprestis rusticus	524
Buprestis humeralis	57	Buprestis humeralis	524

FOURCROY - species signaled as new by «*» FOURCROY - gatunek oznaczony jako nowy przez «*»	Page Strona	GEOFFROY 1799 and 1800 GEOFFROY 1799 i 1800	Page Strona
Bruchus cruciatus	58	Bruchus cruciatus	524
Dyticus hebraicus	70	Dyticus hebraicus	525
Dyticus punctatus	70	Dyticus punctatus	525
Dyticus marmoratus	70	Dyticus marmoratus	525
Cerambyx compressus signaled without «*»	76	Cerambyx compressus	526
Cerambyx dentatus	76	Cerambyx dentatus	526
Cerambyx nebulosus signaled without «*»	77	Cerambyx nebulosus	526
Leptura nebulosa	78	Leptura nebulosa	526
Leptura fulvipes	79	Leptura fulvipes	527
Leptura vidua	82	Leptura vidua	527
Leptura punctuosa	83	Leptura punctuosa	527
Leptura turcica	83	Leptura turcia	528
Leptura fusca (s.a.)	84	Leptura fusca	528
Stenocorus ruber	89	Stenocorus ruber	528
Stenocorus ignitus	89	Stenocorus ignitus	529
Stenocorus funereus	89	Stenocorus funereus	529
Cryptocephalus 10-maculatus	93	Cryptocephalus maculatus	529
Cryptocephalus limbosus	94	Cryptocephalus limbosus	529
Cryptocephalus chermesinus	94	Cryptocephalus chermesinus	530
Cryptocephalus fuscipes	94	Cryptocephalus fuscipes	530
Crioceris spinosissima	96		
Crioceris thoracica	96	Crioceris thoracica	530
Crioceris atrata	96	Crioceris atrata	530
Crioceris paleata signaled without «*»	97	Crioceris paleata	530
Altica aenea	102		
Galeruca viridis	104	Galeruca viridis	531
Galeruca 4-maculata signaled without «*»	104	Galeruca quadrimaculata	531
Chrysomela ferruginea signaled without «*»	110	Chrysomela ferruginea	531
Chrysomela gemellata signaled without «*»	110	Chrysomela gemellata	531
Chrysomela scabra	111	Chrysomela scabra	531
Chrysomela antiqua signaled without «*»	111	Chrysomela antiqua	532
Chrysomela suturata signaled without «*»	111	Chrysomela suturata	532
Chrysomela tulipa signaled without «*»	111	Chrysomela tulipa (complement du texte)	532
Rhinomacer striatus	115	Rhinomacer striatus	533
Rhinomacer fulgidus	116	Rhinomacer fulgidus	533
Curculio scabrosus	126	Curculio scabrosus	534
Curculio contractus	126	Curculio contractus	534
Curculio fuscipes	127	Curculio fuscipes	534

FOURCROY - species signaled as new by «*» FOURCROY - gatunek oznaczony jako nowy przez «*»	Page Strona	GEOFFROY 1799 and 1800 GEOFFROY 1799 i 1800	Page Strona
Curculio punctulatus	132	Curculio punctulatus	534
Curculio cordifer	132	Curculio cordifer	535
Curculio fascianus signaled without «*»	133	Curculio fascianus	535
Bostrichus fuscus	133	Bostricus fuscus	535
Clerus fasciatus	135	Clerus fasciatus	536
Clerus fasciatus varietas thorace rufo	135	Clerus fasciatus thorace rufo	537
Clerus fasciatus varietas niger	135	Clerus fasciatus niger	537
Clerus maculatus	136	Clerus maculatus	537
Antribus fulvus	138		
Antribus connexus	138	Anthribus connexus	537
Antribus nitidus	138	Anthribus nitidus	538
Antribus vittatus	138	Anthribus vittatus	538
Antribus pallidus signaled without «*»	139	Anthribus pallidus	538
Antribus intersectus signaled without «*»	139	Anthribus intersectus	538
Coccinella testudinaria	151		
Coccinella 12-guttata	151	Coccinella guttata	539
Coccinella 16-guttata	151	Coccinella guttata	539
Cantharis variegata	156	Cantharis variegata	539
Tenebrio arenaria	160	Tenebrio arenaria	540
Tenebrio rotundata	160	Tenebrio rotundata	540
Tenebrio globulosa	160	Tenebrio globulosa	540
Tenebrio corulea	160	Tenebrio corulea	540
Staphylinus melanophthalmos	171	Staphylinus melanophthalmos	541
Staphylinus elongatus	171	Staphylinus elongatus	541
Staphylinus angustatus	172	Staphylinus angustatus	542
Staphylinus variegatus	172	Staphylinus variegatus	542
Staphylinus arenarius	172	Staphylinus arenarius	542
Staphylinus melonocephalus	172	Staphylinus melonocephalus	542
Staphylinus nigro-fulvus	173	Staphylinus nigro-fulvus	543
Staphylinus cupreus	173		
Necydalis major	174	Necydalis major	543
Cicada nevroptera	192	Cicada nevroptera	544
Cicada acephala	192	Cicada acephala	544
Cicada tristis	192	Cicada tristis	544
Cicada porrecta	192	Cicada porrecta	544
Cicada dilatata signaled without «*»	193	Cicada dilatata	545
Cimex tridentatus	214	Cimex tridentatus	545
Cimex biclavatus	214	Cimex biclavatus	545

FOURCROY - species signaled as new by «*» FOURCROY - gatunek oznaczony jako nowy przez «*»	Page Strona	GEOFFROY 1799 and 1800 GEOFFROY 1799 i 1800	Page Strona
Phalaena subrubescens	268	Phalaena subrubescens	682
Phalaena inordinata	269	Phalaena inordinata	682
Phalaena obscura	269	Phalaena obscura	683
Phalaena areolata	269	Phalaena areolata	683
Phalaena punctata	270	Phalaena punctata	683
Phalaena monifiliera	271	Phalaena monifiliera	684
Phalaena simplex	271	Phalaena simplex	684
Phalaena fimbriata	276	Phalaena fimbriata	684
Phalaena nayas	276	Phalaena nayas	685
Phalaena Malletina	276	Papilio Malletina	685
Phalaena atomifera	277	Papilio atomifera	685
Phalaena geminata	277	Phalaena geminata	686
Phalaena virginalis	277	Phalaena virginalis	686
Phalaena carthesiana	278	Phalaena carthesiana	686
Phalaena nitidula	278	Phalaena nitidula	686
Phalaena miliata	278		687
Phalaena immutata	278	Phalaena without the specific name (forgotted by GEOFFROY?)	687
Phalaena herbacea	282	Phalaena herbacea	
Attentoin changement de place!	687		
Phalaena alternata	286	Phalaena alternata	688
Phalaena hieroglyphica signaled without «*»	286	Phalaena hieroglyphica	688
Phalaena undulosa signaled without «*»	286	Phalaena undulosa	688
Phalaena syrene signaled without «*»	286	Phalaena syrena	689
Phalaena humeralis	287	Phalaena humeralis	689
Phalaena pilloselae	287	Phalaena pilloselae	689
Phalaena aurantiaca	287	Phalaena aurantiaca	689
Phalaena lunularis	287	Phalaena lunularis	690
Phalaena prolongata signaled without «*»	288	Phalaena prolongata	690
Phalaena asparagi signaled without «*»	288	Phalaena asparagi	690
Phalaena cordigera signaled without «*»	288	Phalaena cordigera	691
Phalaena eremitica	289	Phalaena eremitica	691
Phalaena albeola	289	Phalaena albeola	691
Phalaena zonata	296	Phalaena zonata	
Error of pagination and replacement of species	693		
Phalaena duplicata	306	Phalaena duplicata	694
Phalaena hilaris	306	Phalaena hilaris	694
Phalaena irregularis signaled without «*»	307	Phalaena irregularis	694

FOURCROY - species signaled as new by «*» FOURCROY - gatunek oznaczony jako nowy przez «*»	Page Strona	GEOFFROY 1799 and 1800 GEOFFROY 1799 i 1800	Page Strona
Phalaena fuscoptera signaled without «*»	307	Phalaena fuscoptera	695
Phalaena dianea signaled without «*»	307	Phalaena dianea	695
Phalaena circulata	308	Phalaena circulata	695
Phalaena hesperidea	308	Phalaena hesperidea	696
Phalaena graminea	308	Phalaena graminea	696
Phalaena usta	308	Phalaena deusta	696
Phalaena milissima	309	Phalaena milissima	696
Phalaena heraclitaea	309	Phalaena heraclitaea	697
Phalaena pulchella	309	Phalaena pulchella	697
Phalaena marina	310	Phalaena marina	697
Phalaena chryso-pallida	310	Phalaena chryso-pallida	698
Phalaena antrorum	310	Phalaena antrorum	698
Phalaena nocturna	311	Phalaena nocturna	698
Phalaena mandarina	311	Phalaena mandarina	698
Phalaena ocularis	311	Phalaena ocularis	699
Phalaena pomacea	312	Phalaena pomacea	699
Phalaena columbina	312	Phalaena columbina	700
Phalaena littorea	312	Phalaena lictorea	700
Phalaena multicolor	313	Phalaena multicolor	700
Phalaena fenestralis	313	Phalaena fenestralis	700
Phalaena donzella	313	Phalaena donzella	701
Phalaena prestiosa	313	Phalaena prestiosa	701
Phalaena opalea	314	Phalaena opalea	701
Phalaena focorum	314	Phalaena focorum	702
Phalaena vinosa	314	Phalaena vinosa	702
Phalaena pellicea	315	Phalaena pellicea	702
Phalaena doliata	315	Phalaena doliata	702
Phalaena franciscana	315	Phalaena franciscana	703
Phalaena ferruginea	315	Phalaena ferruginea	703
Phalaena arcuata	316	Phalaena arcuata	703
Phalaena Kermesina	316	Phalaena Kermesina	704
Phalaena hispana	316	Phalaena hispana	704
Phalaena citrella	317	Phalaena citrella	704
Phalaena sinuosa	317	Phalaena sinuosa	704
Phalaena mediata	317	Phalaena mediata	705
Phalaena ovata	318	Phalaena ovata	705
Phalaena modesta	318	Phalaena modesta	705
Phalaena circumscripta	318	Phalaena circumscripta	706
Phalaena auriculata	319	Phalaena auriculata	706

FOURCROY - species signaled as new by «*» FOURCROY - gatunek oznaczony jako nowy przez «*»	Page Strona	GEOFFROY 1799 and 1800 GEOFFROY 1799 i 1800	Page Strona
Phalaena rosacea	319	Phalaena rosacea	706
Phalaena anglica	319	Phalaena anglica	707
Phalaena bidella	320	Phalaena bidella	707
Tinea cinta	336	Tinea cinta	707
Tinea punctulata	337	Tinea punctulata	707
Tinea atratella	337	Tinea atratella	708
Tinea virgata	337	Tinea virgata	708
Tinea vittata	337	Tinea vittata	708
Tinea signatella	338	Tinea signatella	708
Tinea lucidula	338	Tinea lucidula	709
Tinea radiatella	338	Tinea radiatella	709
Tinea scapulata	338	Tinea scapulata	709
Tinea turcica	339	Tinea turcica	709
Tinea crassicornis	339	Tinea crassicornis	710
Tinea purpuratella	339	Tinea purpuratella	710
Tinea cinerata	340	Tinea cinerata	710
Tinea attenuata	340	Tinea attenuata	711
Tinea citrinella	340	Tinea citrinella	711
Tinea pallidula	340	Tinea pallidula	711
Tinea tan	341	Tinea tau	711
Tinea argentinetta	341	Tinea argentinetta	712
Tinea stellata	341	Tinea stellata	712
Tinea aurantiaca	342	Tinea aurentiaca	712
Libellula adelaïs	345	Libellula adelaïs	713
Libellula victoria	348	Libellula victoria	714
Phryganea variegata signaled without «*»	357	Phryganea variegata	714
Phryganea lugubris signaled without «*»	357	Phryganea lugubris	714
Phryganea nervosa signaled without «*»	357	Phryganea nervosa	715
Phryganea atra signaled without «*»	358	Phryganea atra	715
Phryganea galltata signaled without «*»	358	Phryganea guttata	715
Crabro annulatus	362	Crabro annulatus	715
Tenthredo cordigera signaled without «*»	374	Tenthredo cordifera	716
Tenthredo Astroites	375	Tenthredo Astroïtes	716
Tenthredo palmata	375	Tenthredo palmata	716
Tenthredo perlata	375	Tenthredo perlata	717
Tenthredo apicaris signaled without «*»	376	Tenthredo apicaris	717
Tenthredo thoracica signaled without «*»	376	Tenthredo thoracica	717
Tenthredo longicollis	378	Tenthredo longicollis	718
Tenthredo prolongata	379	Tenthredo prolongata	719

FOURCROY - species signaled as new by «*» FOURCROY - gatunek oznaczony jako nowy przez «*»	Page Strona	GEOFFROY 1799 and 1800 GEOFFROY 1799 i 1800	Page Strona
Tenthredo sertifera	378	Tenthredo sertifera	719
Cynips bifasciatus	388	Cynips bifasciatus	720
Cynips eulophus	389	Cynips eulophus	720
Ichneumon punctulatus (s.a.)	407	Ichneumon punctulatus	721
Ichneumon vittatus signaled without «*»	425	Ichneumon vittatus	722
Ichneumon rusticus	426	Ichneumon rusticus	722
Ichneumon quadripes	426	Ichneumon quadripes	723
Ichneumon basilaris	426	Ichneumon basilaris	723
Ichneumon poplitaeus	426	Ichneumon poplitaeus	723
Ichneumon coelestis	427	Ichneumon coelestis	724
Ichneumon flavipes	427	Ichneumon flavipes	724
Ichneumon arlequinatus	427	Ichneumon arlequinatus	724
Ichneumon signatus	428	Ichneumon signatus	724
Ichneumon segmentosus	428	Ichneumon segmentosus	725
Ichneumon petiolatus signaled without «*»	428	Ichneumon petiolatus	725
Ichneumon fasciatus	428	Ichneumon fasciatus	725
Ichneumon bipartitus signaled without «*»	429	Ichneumon bipartitus	726
Vespa sinuata	438	Vespa sinuata	726
Vespa intersecta	439	Vespa intersecta	726
Vespa petiolata	439	Vespa petiolata	727
Vespa fulvipes	439	Vespa fulvipes	727
Vespa capitata signaled without «*»	440	Vespa capitata	728
Apis interrupta	448	Apis interrupta	728
Asilus lacrymosus signaled without «*»	465	Asilus lacrymosus	729
Asilus fulvopterus	466	Asilus fulvopterus	729
Musca conferta signaled without «*»	474	Musca conferta	729
Musca vitrata	475	Musca vitrata	730
Musca turcica	487	Musca turcica	730
Musca doliata	487	Musca doliata	731
Musca adunata	488	Musca adunata	731
Musca smaragdina	492	Musca smaragdina	731
Volucella maculata signaled without «*»	501	Volucella maculata	732
Nemotelus stellaris signaled without «*»	503	Nemotelus stellaris	732
Culex annulatus	516	Culex annulatus	733
Aranea phalangioides signaled without «*»	535	Aranea phalangioides	734

CONCLUSION

Documents found in the archives of the Académie Royale des Sciences, Académie de Médecine and Muséum national d'Histoire naturelle in Paris turned out to be very important both for the history of entomology and contemporary zoological nomenclature. They contributed to a better understanding of two outstanding scientists, Étienne-Louis Geoffroy and Antoine-François Fourcroy, and their relationships. It allowed us to learn about the history of two important works for the history of zoology: *Histoire abrégée des insectes: qui se trouvent aux environs de Paris: dans laquelle ces animaux sont rangés suivant un ordre méthodique* and *Entomologia Parisiensis; sive catalogus insectorum quae in agro Parisiensi reperiuntur; secundum methodum Geoffraeanam in sectiones, genera & species distributus; cui addita sunt nomina trivalia & fere trecentae novae species*. Both of these works played an important role in the introduction of Linnean taxonomy. The reports kept in the library of the Académie des Sciences and the Académie de Médecine allow for the undisputed authorship of *Entomologia Parisiensis* and of the species described therein. In this way, the almost two-century-long dispute over who was the author, Geoffroy or Fourcroy, of the first species descriptions of several dozen taxa was resolved. The importance of historiographic research conducted in various archival units for contemporary zoological nomenclature should also be emphasized.

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Streszczenie

Dwa niepublikowane dokumenty – raporty Société Royale de Médecine i Académie Royale des Sciences na temat *Entomologia Parisiensis* i ich implikacje dla nomenklatury zoologicznej

Opublikowana w 1762 roku przez E.-L. Geoffroy *Histoire abrégée des insectes...* jest jedną z najważniejszych prac zoologii XVIII wieku, zarówno ze względu na liczbę opisanych gatunków, jak i wykorzystanie systemu Linneusza. Jednak opisy zostały opublikowane po francusku, a sama praca miała format, który był niepraktyczny do badań terenowych. W 1785 roku A.-F. Fourcroy opublikował *Entomologia Parisiensis* opartą na *Histoire abrégée des insectes...*, dodając nie tylko opisy łacińskie, ale także kilkaset nowych gatunków. Od tego czasu toczy się spór, czy *Entomologia Parisiensis* jest oryginalnym dziełem, czy jedynie adaptacją *Histoire abrégée des insectes*. Artykuł analizuje raporty Académie Royale des Sciences i Académie royale de Médecine poprzedzające publikację tej pracy. Oryginalność *Entomologia Parisiensis* została wyraźnie wykazana i ustalono, które gatunki należy uznać za opisane przez Fourcroya, a które zostały pierwotnie opisane przez Geoffroya.

Accepted: 1 March 2025; published: 11 March 2025

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